

Shadows of the Past: Exploring the Landscape of Dark Tourism in West Bengal

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Abstract

Dark tourism, also termed thanatourism, refers to travel to sites associated with death, tragedy, violence and human suffering, and has emerged as a significant field of academic inquiry due to its links with memory, heritage, ethics and spatial representation. India's complex historical landscape shaped by colonialism, political movements, conflict, distinctive death rituals, and Tantricism offers substantial scope for dark tourism research. Within this national context, West Bengal presents a distinctive geography of dark tourism, where landscapes of death are deeply embedded in cultural memory and regional identity. This paper examines the potential of dark tourism in West Bengal from a tourism-geographical perspective using primary data as well as secondary data from academic literature, historical documents, tourism reports and archival sources. The study analyses selected sites, namely Dow Hill (Kurseong), South Park Street Cemetery and Alipore Central Jail (Kolkata), Tarapith (Birbhum), Marichjhapi (South 24 Parganas), Plassey (Murshidabad), and Begunkodor (Purulia). Findings reveal fragmented and informal development yet strong potential for thematic dark tourism circuits. Ethical, community-centred and sustainable planning is essential for future development.

Keywords

Dark Tourism, Tourism Geography, Deathscape, Tourism Circuit, SWOT Analysis.

Introduction

Tourism is the fastest growing industry of the twenty-first century which has undergone significant diversification, moving beyond conventional mass tourism towards a range of niche and special interest forms such as ecotourism, heritage tourism, medical tourism, and dark tourism. Among these, dark tourism has emerged as a contested yet increasingly significant field of study within tourism geography and cultural geography. Dark tourism broadly refers to travel to places associated with death, disaster, tragedy, and human suffering (Foley & Lennon, 1996; Stone, 2006). Tourists engaging in dark tourism do so for a variety of reasons, including (a) curiosity and education, (b) personal or emotional connection, (c) cultural and collective identity, and (d) spiritual or moral reflection (Seaton, 1996; Stone & Sharpley, 2008). Although the terminology is relatively recent, the practice itself is not new. Different forms of dark tourism have gained global prominence, including grave and cemetery tourism, prison and persecution site tourism, disaster tourism, political memory tourism, and industrial disaster tourism (Stone, 2006; Light, 2017). For example, Ground Zero of New York is the site of the 9/11 terrorist attacks has turned out to be a popular dark tourism site. At Chernobyl, Ukraine, Tours of the decommissioned Pripyat community are available at the site of the nuclear power plant catastrophe in 1986. Murambi Genocide Memorial that houses the relics of the Rwandan genocide victims from 1994 often visited by tourists. KGB Headquarters in Lithuania is now a museum dedicated to the memory of the genocide victims. The building was formerly a prison and a torture centre. Concentration camps in Poland, known as Auschwitz, were the sites of the mass murder of millions of Jews during the Holocaust. The Peace Memorial Park and Peace Pagoda can be seen in Hiroshima, Japan, the location of the atomic blast that occurred in 1945. Cambodian Museum chronicles the atrocities committed by the Khmer Rouge in the Tuol Sleng prison, which was formerly a school. Jalianwalabag in Punjab, India is known for its massacre of innocents by the British which draws a large number of domestic as well as international tourists throughout the year.

From a geographical perspective, dark tourism sites basically represent distinctive cultural landscapes where space, memory, and meaning intersect. These 'deathscapes' are not merely physical locations but socially and culturally constructed spaces shaped by historical narratives, political power, and collective remembrance. The spatial distribution, accessibility, regional context, and landscape characteristics of such sites play a crucial role in shaping tourism flows and tourists' experiences.

Fig. 1 Dark Tourism Landscape
Dark Tourism Landscape

Source: Authors

In India, dark tourism remains an under-recognized component of tourism planning despite the presence of numerous sites linked to colonial violence, wars, famines, religious death rituals, natural disasters, and political unrests. Scholars have noted that dark tourism in India often exists informally, embedded within pilgrimage tourism, heritage tourism, or historical tourism, rather than as a clearly defined category. India is witnessing a significant rise in dark tourism, with a projected Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 5.1% from 2024 to 2034, surpassing global averages (flexstates.com). The global dark tourism market was valued at USD 31.89 billion in 2023 and is expected to reach USD 38.64 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 2.9% from 2024 to 2030. (Grand View Research, 2023).

Table no. 1 Dark Tourism Market Growth (2023–2030)
[Based on CAGR of 2.9%]

Year	Market Size (USD Billion)
2023	31.89 (Actual Value)
2024	32.82 (as forecasted)
2025	33.77 (as forecasted)
2026	34.75 (as forecasted)
2027	35.75 (as forecasted)
2028	36.78 (as forecasted)
2029	37.84 (as forecasted)
2030	38.92 (as forecasted)

Source: Grand View Research report (2023)

Fig. 2 Global dark tourism market size forecast (2023-2030)

Source: Made by the authors on the basis of GVR Report

West Bengal occupies a unique position in this context. The state's geography encompasses the Himalayan foothills, fertile alluvial plains, urban colonial centers, riverine landscapes, and the fragile Sundarbans delta. Its history includes colonial encounters, revolutionary nationalism, religious traditions centered on death and sacrifice, refugee movements, and political violence. Despite this, tourism development in West Bengal has largely focused on culture, festivals, hill tourism, and coastal tourism, leaving dark tourism sites almost marginal or unexplored.

Objective of study

This paper aims to explore the potentiality of dark tourism in West Bengal from a tourism geographical perspective. The specific objectives are:

1. to identify major potential dark tourism sites in West Bengal;
2. to analyze their spatial characteristics, cultural landscapes, and locational context; and
3. to assess their prospects for responsible and sustainable tourism development.

Review of Literature

The concept of dark tourism gained formal academic recognition in the mid 1990s when Foley and Lennon (1996) introduced the term to describe tourism associated with sites of death, disaster, and atrocity. Closely related terms such as thanatourism (Seaton, 1996), morbid tourism (Blom, 2000), and atrocity tourism (Ashworth & Hartmann, 2005) have been used interchangeably in the literature, reflecting the conceptual ambiguity of the field. Stone (2006) defines dark tourism as travel to sites associated with death, suffering, and the seemingly macabre, emphasizing that such sites vary in intensity, purpose, and interpretation. Stone's (2006) dark tourism spectrum remains one of the most influential theoretical frameworks, categorizing sites from 'light' (entertainment oriented) to 'dark' (sites of mass death and suffering). However, Sharpley and Stone (2009) argue that dark tourism should not be understood solely through site typologies, but rather through the interaction between visitor motivations, site characteristics, and socio-cultural context. Biran and Hyde (2013) further critique typological rigidity, suggesting that dark tourism experiences are subjective, relational, and culturally embedded.

Early explanations of dark tourism demand emphasized morbid curiosity as a dominant motivation (Blom, 2000). Later studies, however, reveal a more complex motivational structure, including education, remembrance, identity construction, moral obligation, and existential reflection (Stone & Sharpley, 2008; Hyde & Harman, 2011). Dark tourism is increasingly conceptualized as an emotionally charged experience through which visitors negotiate their understanding of mortality and collective memory (Stone, 2011; Sharma & Nayak, 2019). Ethical concerns occupy a central position in dark tourism scholarship. Ashworth and Hartmann (2005) highlight the moral dilemmas associated with commodifying sites of human suffering, while Timothy (2011) emphasizes issues of authenticity, respect, and stakeholder representation. Stone (2013) argues that dark tourism scholarship must critically examine how death is mediated and marketed, rather than merely cataloguing sites. These ethical concerns are particularly pronounced in postcolonial and politically sensitive contexts. From a tourism geographical standpoint, dark tourism sites are understood as 'deathscapes'—spaces where landscape, memory, power, and representation intersect (Stone, 2013). The spatiality of dark tourism is shaped by location, accessibility, regional context, and surrounding land use. Light (2017) demonstrates that urban dark tourism sites often benefit from infrastructure, interpretative facilities, and visibility, whereas rural and remote sites face challenges related to accessibility and policy neglect.

Geographers also emphasize that dark tourism sites are frequently contested spaces where official narratives may silence alternative or marginalized histories. Such dissonant heritage landscapes require careful interpretation to avoid reinforcing dominant power structures (Ashworth & Hartmann, 2005; Sharpley, 2009). Dark tourism research in India remains limited and largely exploratory. Existing studies focus primarily on conceptual discussions or inventories of potential sites (Dhatrak, 2020; Jain, Madireddy, & Rao, 2020). Sharma (2017, 2022) argues that dark tourism already exists in India in fragmented and informal forms, often embedded within pilgrimage tourism, heritage tourism, or political memory, but lacks formal recognition and ethical policy frameworks. A critical issue highlighted in Indian scholarship is the inappropriateness of uncritically applying Eurocentric dark tourism frameworks to non-Western societies (Light, 2017; Sharma, 2017). In India, death is often publicly ritualized and culturally integrated, as seen in religious landscapes such as Varanasi and Tarapith. This challenges Western notions of death as hidden or taboo and necessitates culturally grounded theoretical approaches. Empirical studies on tourist perception indicate a growing acceptance of dark tourism in India, particularly when it is framed around education, remembrance, and heritage rather than entertainment or spectacle (Sarkar, Chakraborty, & Valeri, 2021). These findings suggest that dark tourism in India has strong potential, provided it is developed within culturally sensitive, ethical, and sustainability-oriented frameworks.

Methodology

The present study is based on primary as well as secondary data sets. Field survey has been conducted in selected dark tourism sites in order to understand the current scenario and future potentiality. Data have been collected directly from field as well as secondary sources such as peer-reviewed journals, books, edited volumes, government tourism reports, historical records, census documents, newspaper archives, and credible online databases related to tourism and heritage studies. The methodological framework is qualitative and analytical. Potential dark tourism sites in West Bengal were identified based on historical association with death, tragedy, violence, suffering and collective trauma. Each site was then analyzed in terms of location, accessibility, regional setting and physical landscape. Tourism potentiality was evaluated considering infrastructure, visitor accessibility, interpretative scope, ethical sensitivity, and sustainability concerns. The selected sites include Dow Hill (Kurseong), South Park Street Cemetery (Kolkata), Tarapith (Birbhum), Marichjhapi (South 24 Pargana), Alipore Central Jail (Kolkata), Begunkodor (Purulia) and Plassey (Nadia) were chosen to ensure spatial diversity across West Bengal and represent multiple dark tourism typologies.

Result and Discussion

Spatial Distribution of Dark Tourism Sites in West Bengal

Dark tourism sites in West Bengal are spatially dispersed across different physiographic and cultural regions: the Darjeeling Himalayan hills (Dow Hill), the metropolitan core of Kolkata (South Park Street Cemetery and Alipore Central Jail), the Rarh and Bhagirathi plains (Plassey, Tarapith), and the Sundarbans delta (Marichjhapi). This spatial diversity provides opportunities for regional tourism circuits and thematic linkages.

Site-wise Analysis

4.2.1 Dow Hill, Kurseong (Haunted Landscape Tourism) (26.8991° N, 88.2961° E)

Located in the Darjeeling Himalayan foothills, Dow Hill is associated with ghost stories and unexplained incidents linked to colonial-era institutions. The dense forest cover, misty climate, and relative isolation contribute to its eerie landscape character. From a geographical perspective, the site's physical environment plays a crucial role in shaping its dark tourism image. Dow Hill has potential for controlled ghost tourism and heritage interpretation, provided safety and ethical representation are ensured.

4.2.2 South Park Street Cemetery, Kolkata (Cemetery and Colonial Heritage Tourism) (22° 32' 47.6" N, 88° 21' 37.4" E)

Established in 1767, South Park Street Cemetery represents colonial mortality in a tropical environment. Its large mausoleums, inscriptions, and funerary architecture reflect the spatial relationship between colonial power, disease ecology, and urban form. Located in central Kolkata, the site has high accessibility and strong potential for educational dark tourism, heritage walks, and urban cultural tourism.

Plate 1: Some glimpses of the dark tourism sites

Source: Authors

4.2.3 Tarapith (Religious Deathscape and Pilgrimage-Dark Tourism Nexus) (24.1140° N, 87.7991° E)

Tarapith is a major Shakti pilgrimage centre associated with tantric rituals and cremation grounds.

Fig. 3 Dark Tourism location in West Bengal

Source: Authors

Tarapith exemplifies the overlap between pilgrimage tourism and dark tourism in India. Tarapith is the most celebrated and revered Satipith of Bengal. It is believed that the eye ball of Sati fell here. It attracts thousands of devotees each day and during special occasions like *Koushiki Amabasya*, this places receives nearly a lakh visitors coming from all over Bengal and even neighbouring states. Considered to be a seat of *Tantrics*, Tarapith is considered as one of the most important religious destinations of Eastern India.

4.2.4 Marichjhapi (Political Massacre and Memory Tourism)(22.1076° N, 88.9508° E)

Marichjhapi, located in the Sundarbans delta, is associated with the violent eviction and death of refugees in 1979. The site represents a silenced and contested memory landscape. Its remote location, fragile ecosystem, and lack of infrastructure pose challenges, yet from a geographical and ethical perspective, it holds potential for remembrance tourism and human rights education.

4.2.5 Alipore Central Jail, Kolkata (Prison and Revolutionary Heritage Tourism) (22°31'31"N 88°20'24"E)

Alipore Central Jail played a significant role during India's freedom struggle, housing political prisoners and execution sites. Located within the urban fabric of Kolkata, it has high tourism accessibility. Partial conversion into a museum indicates strong potential for prison tourism and nationalist heritage tourism.

4.2.6 Plassey (Battlefield Tourism)(23° 48' 0" N, 88° 15' 0" E)

The Battle of Plassey (1757) marked a decisive turning point in Indian history. Located in Nadia district along the Bhagirathi River, Plassey represents battlefield tourism linked with colonial conquest. Despite its historical importance, the site remains underdeveloped, lacking interpretation centres and structured tourism facilities.

4.2.7 Begunkodor (23° 21' 10.08" N, 86° 3' 23.76" E):

Haunted Landscape Tourism

Begunkodor (near Jhalda in Purulia) has a strong dark-tourism niche because its railway station became nationally known as a "haunted station" after alleged paranormal rumours in the late 1960s, followed by a long closure and a later reopening (2009). That unusual "abandonment–return" storyline, along with the continued folklore around sightings and fear after sunset, creates a ready-made narrative for legend-tripping, paranormal curiosity, and heritage storytelling- key drivers of dark tourism demand.

Its potential increases if packaged as a micro-circuit with Purulia’s broader attractions (rural/tribal landscape, hills/forests, cultural tourism), but it needs careful management: safe night-time arrangements, ethical interpretation (myth vs reality), community benefit-sharing, and visitor guidance to avoid sensationalism or harassment of locals and staff. The ethical concerns around dark tourism are especially salient in India where cultural norms around death, mourning, and memory are deeply rooted. There is a thin line between respectful remembrance and voyeurism. Emotional responses from tourists found to be ranged from empathy and sorrow to detachment and even fascination during verbal interactions. Issues of representation and storytelling are also crucial. For example, the Jallianwala Bagh site has been critiqued for being too sanitized and lacking emotional depth, while the Partition Museum has been praised for its narrative-driven, emotionally engaging exhibitions. Digital platforms have played a significant role in popularizing dark tourism sites in India. YouTube documentaries, facebook reels, Instagram posts, and travel blogs have contributed to increased visibility and accessibility of these destinations. Virtual tours have also emerged as a means of engaging with traumatic history from afar, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. The commercialization of dark tourism sites in India is increasingly evident. Souvenir shops, entry fees, and guided tours suggest a commodification of tragedy. While this supports local economies and heritage conservation, it raises concerns about trivializing or distorting historical facts.

4.3 Tourism Circuits and Spatial Linkages

Based on spatial proximity and thematic similarity, the following dark tourism circuits may be proposed: i) Colonial Kolkata Dark Tourism Circuit: South Park Street Cemetery – Alipore Central Jail ii) Colonial Conquest and Resistance Circuit: Plassey – Kolkata iii) Sacred Deathscape Circuit: Tarapith – nearby other Shakti pilgrimage centres including Nalhatেশwari, Kankalitala, Bakreshwar, Attahas (Phullara), and Sainthia iv) Political Memory and Marginalized History Circuit: Marichjhapi – Sundarbans cultural landscape.

At first, each of these dark tourism circuits may be incorporated with existing circuits of identical nature in order to give it a boost towards popularity. As for example, the *Sacred Deathscape Circuit* centring Tarapith may incorporate other notable religious or cultural tourism destinations including Birchandrapur (Vaishnava Sacred site), Sainthia (Satipith), Karnasubarna (Satipith), Mallarpur (Shaiva pith) etc. Similarly *Political Memory and Marginalized History Circuit* centring Marichjhapi may incorporate Kakdwip (related with the memory of *Tebhaga Andolon* or Tebhaga Protests), Jatar Deul (religious tourism destination), Sagar Island (Spiritual tourism destination) etc.

A micro-level perception survey conducted among tourists in Tarapith in 2025 sought to identify key motivational factors influencing visitation beyond the conventional factor i.e. religious devotion. The findings indicate that *Tantricism* and occult practices constitute the second most significant motivational factor after religious belief. Importantly, 9.42% of the surveyed visitors identified this dimension as the second strongest attribute of the destination.

Table 2 Accommodation scenario of Tarapith

Year	Number of Hotels	Number of Hotel bed
2017	270	8100
2021	303	9690
2025	359	11771

Source: 2017 data - Field survey by the first author, 2021 and 2025 data – TRDA Office

Fig. 4 Accommodation Scenario of Tarapith, Source: Authors

This perception underscores Tarapith's distinctive appeal rooted in esoteric rituals, mysticism, and symbolic associations with death, thereby revealing substantial potential for the development of niche and exclusive dark tourism.

Fig. 5 Tourist' Motivation

Source: Authors

5. SWOT Analysis for Initiating Full-Fledged Dark Tourism in West Bengal

A SWOT analysis was conducted after field survey at Tarapith- a prominent religious as well as dark tourism sites of West Bengal and after going through the extensive literatures and secondary data which reveals the following-

Strengths

1. West Bengal has a deeply layered historical geography involving colonialism, freedom struggle, political movements, religious death rituals, and social trauma.
2. The state shows spatial diversity of dark heritage landscapes (urban, rural, hill, riverine, deltaic).
3. Many dark tourism elements are already embedded within heritage, pilgrimage, and cultural tourism.
4. High educational, commemorative, and research value of death-related heritage.
5. Strong domestic tourist base with cultural and historical orientation.

Weaknesses

1. Absence of a formal policy framework dedicated to dark tourism.
2. Lack of interpretation infrastructure (museums, narratives, signage, trained guides).
3. Uneven tourism infrastructure across regions.
4. Ethical sensitivity and contested historical narratives.
5. Limited coordination between tourism, culture, education, and local governance bodies.
6. Introduce capacity-building programmes for guides and local stakeholders.

Opportunities

1. Growing demand for experience-based, meaningful, and reflective tourism.
2. Rising academic interest in memory, heritage, and trauma landscapes.
3. Scope for digital interpretation and low-impact tourism models.
4. Potential for community-based and inclusive tourism development.
5. Alignment with national and global sustainable and responsible tourism agendas.

Threats

1. Risk of over-commercialization and sensationalism.
2. Political resistance and selective historical interpretation.
3. Environmental vulnerability in ecologically sensitive areas.
4. Social and moral opposition to commodifying death-related spaces.
5. Institutional inertia and lack of long-term planning.

Major Policy Recommendations

On the basis of the SWOT analysis, the following major policies are being recommended in order to properly utilize the strength, neutralize the weaknesses, understand the threat and take the opportunities under consideration-

1. Officially recognize dark tourism as a sub-sector under the State Tourism Policy.
2. Use thematic and circuit-based planning instead of isolated site development.
3. Integrate dark tourism interpretation within existing heritage and cultural tourism schemes.
4. Promote educational tourism partnerships with universities, colleges, and research institutions.
5. Establish a Dark Tourism Policy & Ethics Framework at the state level.
6. Create standardized interpretation guidelines focusing on education and remembrance.
7. Adopt region-specific development models (urban, rural, fragile).
8. Form an interdisciplinary advisory body (historians, geographers, sociologists, planners).
9. Position dark tourism as educational and commemorative, not entertainment-driven.
10. Integrate dark tourism into school and university fieldwork curricula.
11. Invest in digital storytelling, virtual tours, and archival interpretation.
12. Encourage community participation in guiding, storytelling, and conservation.
13. Promote low-volume, high-value tourism to ensure sustainability.
14. Enforce strict ethical guidelines against sensational marketing.
15. Ensure multi-vocal and transparent historical narratives.
16. Apply carrying capacity and environmental regulation norms.
17. Conduct stakeholder consultations and public awareness programmes.
18. Introduce monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for dark tourism projects.

Conclusion

West Bengal possesses significant yet underutilized potential for dark tourism. The state's diverse physical geography and layered historical experiences have produced a wide range of deathscapes, from haunted forests and colonial cemeteries to sacred cremation grounds, prisons, massacre sites, and battlefields. From a tourism geographical perspective, the spatial distribution and regional diversity of these sites offer strong possibilities for thematic tourism circuits and regional development. However, the development of dark tourism must be approached with caution and ethical responsibility. Tourism planning should prioritize education, remembrance, and cultural sensitivity rather than sensationalism. Community participation, accurate historical interpretation, and environmental sustainability are essential, particularly in fragile regions such as the Sundarbans. Integrating dark tourism into West Bengal's tourism framework can diversify the state's tourism portfolio and enhance heritage awareness, provided it is guided by context-specific, ethical, and sustainable planning principles.

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